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MASTER OF ENVIRONMENT AND NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT

KEITH D. CAMEÑA

**AN ASSESSMENT OF THE INFLUENCE OF FOREST MANAGEMENT
AGREEMENTS, LOG PRODUCTION, PROVINCIAL INCOME CLASS, AND
SLOPE ON PHILIPPINE FOREST CHANGE FROM 2000 TO 2021**

Special Problem Adviser:
LEONIDA A. BUGAYONG, Ph.D.
Faculty of Management and Development Studies

19 May 2023

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Acceptance Page

This Special Problem titled "**AN ASSESSMENT OF THE INFLUENCE OF FOREST MANAGEMENT AGREEMENTS, LOG PRODUCTION, PROVINCIAL INCOME CLASS, AND SLOPE ON PHILIPPINE FOREST CHANGE FROM 2000 TO 2021**" is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management.

LEONIDA A. BUGAYONG
Faculty-in-charge,
ENRM 290 (Special Problem)

(Date)

KARL ABELARD VILLEGAS JR.
Program Chair

(Date)

JOANE V. SERRANO
Dean
Faculty of Management and Development Studies

(Date)

Declaration

This is to certify that:

- I. The Special Problem comprises only my original work towards the MENRM except where indicated in the Preface.
- II. Due acknowledgment has been made in the text to all other material used.
- III. The Special Problem is fewer than 25,000 words in length, exclusive of tables, maps, bibliographies and appendices.

KEITH D. CAMEÑA
Name

Biographical Sketch

Keith D. Cameña is an architect and urban planner, born in Iloilo City in 1980. After completing his bachelor's degree in Architecture at the University of San Agustin Iloilo, he earned his Urban and Regional Planning diploma from the University of the Philippines Visayas.

Throughout his career, Keith has worked on various projects ranging from city- scale planning to agro-industrial buildings to small houses. He is passionate about creating sustainable, livable communities that balance the needs of people, the environment, and the economy.

One of Keith's most recent projects was the Iloilo City Public Transport Route Plan. The project was part of the national government's Public Utility Vehicle Modernization Program. The project will secure a public transport investment of four billion pesos.

He is a member of several professional organizations, including the United Architects of the Philippines and the Transportation Science Society of the Philippines.

In his free time, Keith enjoys music, movies, dining, traveling with his family, and supporting the biking community that promotes sustainable development and urban revitalization.

Dedicated to
Reji Patch and Ninfa Annan

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ABSTRACT

This study discusses the impact of four variables on stable forests, forest loss, forest gain, and forest disturbance. It used multiple regression analysis to predict the forest change based on (1) the land area covered by Integrated Forest Management Agreements in 2010, (2) log production in 2010, (3) provincial income class, and (4) the share of land area over 18 percent slope. The results showed that only two variables, provincial income class and share of land area over an 18 percent slope, significantly impacted the prediction of stable forests. Additionally, only one variable significantly impacted the prediction of forest loss, and only one variable impacted the prediction of forest gain. Two variables significantly impacted the prediction of forest disturbance. Overall, the study provides insights into the factors that affect forest change in the Philippines and the importance of considering multiple variables when analyzing the impact of human activities on forests.

The findings can inform policymakers and stakeholders in deciding on forest management and conservation in the country.

Keywords: stable forest, forest loss, forest gain, forest disturbance, forest management agreements, log production, provincial income class, slope

INTRODUCTION

Background

The Philippines is an archipelagic country known for its rich biodiversity and abundant forest resources. However, these forests have faced massive deforestation over the years due to various human activities such as logging, converting forests to agricultural lands, mining, and urbanization. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), the Philippines lost 47,000 hectares of forest area per year between 1990 and 2000 (FAO, 2020, p. 140).

Forest management agreements (FMAs) have been implemented in the Philippines since 1999 (DENR, 1999) as a means of sustainable forest management. These agreements are contracts between the government and private entities, allowing them to manage and utilize a specific forestland area for a certain period. However, the effectiveness of these agreements in conserving the forests and reducing deforestation remains a matter of debate.

Furthermore, forest change is affected by various factors such as log production, provincial income class, and slope. Understanding the relationship between these factors and forest change can help policymakers and forest managers formulate effective conservation and management strategies.

Significance of the Study

The study on Philippine forest change in the 2000–2021 period and its relationship with FMAs, log production, provincial income class, and slope (steepness) is significant for several reasons. First, the study can provide an

updated and comprehensive understanding of the status of the country's forests, including the rate of deforestation, the remaining forest cover, and the spatial distribution of forest cover and changes. Second, the study can help evaluate the effectiveness of FMAs in conserving forests and reducing deforestation. The findings can inform policymakers and forest managers of the strengths and weaknesses of the current FMA system and suggest possible improvements. Third, the study can help identify the factors contributing to forest change, such as log production, provincial income class, and slope. This information can be used to design and implement targeted conservation and management strategies considering deforestation's specific conditions and drivers in different areas. Overall, this study can contribute to the conservation and sustainable management of forests in the Philippines, which are essential for biodiversity conservation, climate change mitigation, and ecosystem services to local communities.

Research Questions and Objectives

The research questions and objectives of this study on the influence of FMAs, log production, provincial income class, and slope on Philippine forest change from 2000 to 2021, specifically on forest stability, forest loss, forest gain, and forest disturbance, are as follows:

Research questions

1. What is the extent of forest change in the Philippines from 2000 to 2021 regarding forest stability, loss, gain, and disturbance?
2. What is the relationship between FMAs and forest change in the Philippines from 2000 to 2021?

3. How does log production influence forest change in the Philippines from 2000 to 2021?
4. What is the impact of provincial income class on forest change in the Philippines from 2000 to 2021?
5. How does slope affect forest change in the Philippines from 2000 to 2021?

Objectives

1. Assess the extent and patterns of forest change in the Philippines from 2000 to 2021, specifically focusing on forest stability, loss, gain, and disturbance.
2. Examine the relationship between FMAs and forest change in the Philippines from 2000 to 2021 and identify potential factors that may influence this relationship.
3. Evaluate the impact of log production on forest change in the Philippines from 2000 to 2021 and identify any potential favorable or adverse effects.
4. Investigate the role of provincial income class in forest change in the Philippines from 2000 to 2021 and identify any potential disparities between different income classes.
5. Analyze the effect of slope on forest change in the Philippines from 2000 to 2021 and identify any potential patterns or trends.

Overall, this study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors that influence forest change in the Philippines and to inform policies and strategies for sustainable forest management and conservation.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

Several factors limit the scope of this study on the influence of FMAs, log production, provincial income class, and slope on Philippine forest change from 2000 to 2021, specifically on forest stability, loss, gain, and disturbance.

Firstly, the study is restricted by the availability and quality of data on forest change, FMAs, log production, provincial income class, and slope. The data used in this study is derived from various sources, including remote sensing data, government reports, and statistical databases. The accuracy and reliability of this data may be subject to limitations and errors, which could affect the validity of the study's findings.

Secondly, the study is limited by its focus on a specific period (2000–2021) and geographical region (the Philippines). The factors influencing forest change may vary depending on the location and period, and this study's findings may not be generalizable to other regions or periods.

Thirdly, the study is constrained by its analytical approach. The statistical methods used in this study, such as regression analysis and geographic information systems (GIS), have their limitations and assumptions. The study's results may be subject to biases or confounding factors not accounted for in the analysis.

Fourthly, the study may only consider some factors influencing forest change in the Philippines. Other factors, such as climate change, natural disasters, and population growth, may also impact forest change but are not explicitly included in this study.

In summary, while this study provides insights into the influence of FMAs,

log production, provincial income class, and slope on Philippine forest change from 2000 to 2021, its findings should be interpreted with caution due to the limitations of its scope and data sources. Further research is necessary to expand and confirm these findings and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing forest change in the Philippines.

Theoretical Framework

The study aims to assess the impact of FMAs, log production, provincial income class, and slope on forest change in the Philippines from 2000 to 2021. The theoretical frameworks that inform this research are those related to environment and natural resource management: the sustainable forest management paradigm, political ecology perspective, economic theory of natural resource management, and land-use change and forestry framework.

The sustainable forest management paradigm emphasizes using forest resources to benefit present and future generations (FAO, 2019). This paradigm recognizes that forests provide a range of ecosystem services, including biodiversity conservation, carbon sequestration, and the provision of timber and non-timber forest products. The sustainable forest management paradigm promotes the conservation and protection of forests while ensuring that they are used sustainably.

The political ecology perspective emphasizes the role of social and political factors in shaping environmental policies and practices. This perspective recognizes that environmental issues are not just technical problems but are deeply intertwined with social and political relations. The political ecology perspective emphasizes the need to examine the power relations that shape forest

management policies and practices and to ensure that these policies and practices are equitable and sustainable (Benjaminsen & Svarstad, 2019).

The economic theory of natural resource management emphasizes the importance of incorporating economic incentives and disincentives into forest management policies (Kneese, 1988). This theory recognizes that economic factors are vital in using and managing natural resources. The economic theory of natural resource management emphasizes the need to ensure that the costs and benefits of forest use are distributed fairly among different stakeholders and that economic incentives are used to encourage sustainable forest management practices.

The land-use change and forestry framework recognizes that environmental, economic, and social factors influence forest change (Lambin, Geist, & Leper, 2003). This framework emphasizes the importance of examining the drivers of forest change, such as deforestation and afforestation, and the implications for ecosystem services and human well-being. The land-use change and forestry framework also emphasizes the importance of spatial analysis and the use of GIS to understand the spatial relationships between forest change and the variables of interest in this study.

Overall, the theoretical frameworks that underpin this research provide a comprehensive understanding of the complex interactions between environmental, economic, and social factors that influence forest change in the Philippines. By examining the impact of FMAs, log production, provincial income class, and slope on forest stability, loss, gain, and disturbance, this study can provide valuable insights for developing policies and interventions to promote sustainable forest management in the Philippines.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Forest Change in the Philippines from 2000 to 2021

The Philippines is known for its vast and diverse forests, which are crucial to its ecological, economic, and social development. However, the Philippines' forests have been experiencing significant changes over the past two decades, influenced by factors such as FMAs, log production, provincial income class, and slope.

According to a study the Philippines lost an estimated 500,000 hectares of its forest cover between 1990 and 2005 (Carandang, Bugayong, Dolom, Garcia, & Villanueva, 2013, p. 19), primarily due to the conversion of forests to other land uses such as agriculture, mining, and urbanization. Forest loss was exceptionally high in low-income provinces and regions with high slope gradients, with more economic pressure to convert forests to other land uses.

Another study (Guiang, Borlagdan, & Pulhin, 2001) examined the drivers of forest degradation and loss in the Philippines between 1900 and 1999. The study found that forest degradation was primarily caused by logging and other human activities, while forest loss was mainly due to agricultural expansion and urbanization. The study also found that forest degradation was often attributed to poverty with high upland population growth and lack of "operational and effective on-site management systems."

The Philippine government has recently implemented various forest management policies and programs to reduce forest loss and promote sustainable forest management. For example, the Forest Management Bureau (FMB) has implemented FMAs with local communities and indigenous peoples, allowing them

to manage and benefit from forest resources sustainably (DENR, 2004).

Despite these efforts, forest change in the Philippines remains a significant challenge. Further research is needed to understand the drivers of forest change and identify effective strategies to mitigate its impact. Future studies could examine the effectiveness of FMAs and other forest conservation programs in promoting forest stability and reducing forest loss, as well as the socioeconomic factors that influence forest change in the Philippines.

Deforestation and Land-use

The Philippines has undergone significant changes in its forest cover from 2000 to 2021, with a notable decrease due to various factors such as commodity-driven deforestation, shifting agriculture, forestry, and urbanization (GFW, 2023). These changes have led to environmental, social, and economic implications that have affected the country's sustainable development.

According to data from the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA, 2019), the country's tree-cover area increased from 6.5 million hectares in 2010 to 7.8 million hectares in 2015, indicating a net gain of 1.3 million hectares or an average annual increase equal to four percent. The PSA also reported that from 2010 to 2015, that this increase was offset by the annual average managed regression of around 6,000 hectares, amounting to 42,000 hectares within the period.

Another study (Garrity, Kummer, & Guiang, 1993) showed that the country's forest cover decreased from 70 percent in 1900 to only 25.9 percent in 1980, primarily due to deforestation caused by commercial logging, agricultural expansion, and infrastructure development. The study also found that illegal logging and mining activities fragmented, degraded, and threatened the remaining

forests.

Recent studies have examined the drivers of forest change in the Philippines and identified various factors contributing to forest loss and degradation. For instance, a study (Rebugio, et al., 2007) found that forest loss was mainly caused by agricultural expansion, urbanization, and infrastructure development, while forest degradation was primarily due to logging and other human activities.

To address the challenges of forest change in the Philippines, the government has implemented various policies and programs to promote sustainable forest management and conservation. These initiatives include the National Greening Program, which aimed to plant 1.5 billion trees in 1.5 million hectares of degraded lands from 2011 to 2016 (Office of the President of the Philippines, 2011). Another is the Community-based Forest Management Program, which grants communities and indigenous peoples access to forest resources and empowers them to manage the land sustainably.

In summary, the Philippines has undergone significant changes in its forest cover, with deforestation, forest degradation, and land use changes as the primary drivers. However, the government's efforts to promote sustainable forest management and conservation have also been significant, indicating a growing awareness of the importance of forests for ecological, social, and economic development.

Global Forest Change Dataset

Potapov, et al. (The Global 2000–2020 Land Cover and Land Use Change Dataset Derived From the Landsat Archive: First Results, 2022) measured how

much tree cover has changed worldwide (excluding Antarctica and some Arctic islands) from 2000 to 2020. The collaboration between organizations such as the Global Land Analysis and Discovery (GLAD) lab at the University of Maryland, Google, the United States Geological Survey (USGS), and the National Aeronautics and Space Administration) NASA created the product dataset.

The dataset was made by using information about the height of trees in different areas, which was measured using a particular instrument called the Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation (GEDI), which is on board the International Space Station. The GEDI uses lasers to measure the height of trees worldwide, between 52 degrees north and 52 degrees south. This information was combined with other data from a satellite called Landsat, which takes pictures of the earth over time, to create maps of where there is tree cover in the years 2000 and 2020.

To find out how much tree cover has changed, the researchers compared the maps from 2000 to 2020 and looked for areas where trees had either grown or been cut down. They only counted significant changes in tree height, not small changes that might be "noise" in the data.

METHODOLOGY

Definitions

This study used the exact forest definitions in the paper by Potapov, et al. (2022).

Forest

Potapov et al. defined a forest as an area with trees at least five meters tall at the Landsat pixel scale, including various types of forests, agroforestry, orchards, and natural tree regrowth¹. This definition differs from the definition used by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) in that it includes trees outside of forests and excludes temporarily unstocked forest areas. The study did not use the tree canopy cover criterion to define the extent of the forest.

Forest gain

In the same research, forest gain was counted if a pixel had a height of at least five meters in 2020 and either (1) had a forest height of less than five meters in 2000 or (2) had a net forest height increase from 2000 to 2020 of at least 100 percent. In other words, they defined forest gain as an increase in woody vegetation height from 2000 to 2020 in areas that did not previously meet the definition of forest (i.e., had a height of less than five meters in 2000).

¹ The data accounts for vegetation ≥ 5 meters in height but does not differentiate between woody plants, bamboo, or palm.

Forest loss

The authors defined forest loss as areas of forest where the woody vegetation height value for a given year was ≥ 5 meters but decreased by ≥ 50 percent compared to the woody vegetation height value in the year 2000 or decreased below the five meters threshold.

Forest disturbance and stable forest

Forest disturbance was counted when there was forest loss between 2001 and 2020. Additionally, the annual forest loss data allowed for detecting repeated forest change events — i.e., disturbance. Pixels with no indication of forest loss and overlapping ranges of modeled forest height for 2000–2003 and 2017–2020 intervals were counted as stable forests.

Research Design

This research examines the influence of Integrated Forest Management Agreements (IFMAs)², log production, provincial income class, and slope on forest change in the Philippines from 2000 to 2021. The study design utilizes secondary data to analyze patterns and relationships among the variables of interest.

The population of interest for this study is all provinces in the Philippines, which was determined by the availability of data and reporting at this governance

² IFMA is introduced here as a specific variable, as opposed to the general forest management agreement or tenurial instruments referred to in the preceding sections.

level. The study uses multiple regression analysis to examine the relationships among the independent and dependent variables, controlling for potential confounding factors.

The dependent variable in this study is forest change, specifically stable forest extents, forest loss, forest gain, and forest disturbance. Forest change data is from the satellite imagery products of the studies of Potapov, et al. (2022) and Hansen, et al. (High-Resolution Global Maps of 21st-Century Forest Cover Change, 2013).

This study's independent variables of interest are IFMAs, log production, provincial income class, and slope. IFMA is measured as a continuous variable indicating the extent the government gives to the private entity to manage a particular forested area. Log production is measured as the volume of timber harvested from a province in 2010. Provincial income class is measured as a categorical variable indicating the relative economic development of the province. Finally, the slope is measured as a continuous variable indicating the share of provincial land area with over 18 percent steepness.

The research design uses a combination of descriptive statistics, regression analysis, and GIS techniques to analyze the data.

Data

Data collection

This research data is collected from various sources, including government reports, statistical databases, and satellite imagery. The FMB (2010 Philippine Forestry Statistics) report is the data source on IFMAs and log production, and the

Statement of Receipts and Expenditures (BLGF, 2022) is the data source on the provincial income class.

The forest change data is obtained using satellite images from multiple sources, including the Global Land Cover and Land Use Change 2000–2020 (see Figure 4 and Figure 5 in APPENDICES), Global Forest Change 2000–2019, and Global Forest Watch (GFW, 2023). The data is analyzed to identify forest stability, loss, gain, and disturbance areas.

Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (Hole-filled SRTM for the globe Version 4, 2008) data is used to obtain slope data in Quantum GIS (QGIS) software. The process involves downloading the SRTM's digital elevation model (DEM), importing it into QGIS, and using the Raster Terrain Analysis tool to calculate slope values. The tool calculates the slope by analyzing the change in elevation between neighboring pixels in the DEM (QGIS, n.d.). The resulting slope values can be reclassified into categories (under 3 percent, 3–8 percent, 8–18 percent, or over 18 percent slope).

The administrative boundary data is obtained from the Humanitarian Data Exchange (HDX) website. This process involves navigating to the HDX website, selecting the desired country from the map or list provided, and choosing the specific administrative level of interest, in this case, the province. The website users can choose from various file formats to download, such as shapefile, GeoJSON, or KML, all of which can be processed in QGIS.

Data analysis

The data analysis for this research involves multiple regression analysis, with the dependent variables being forest stability, forest loss, forest gain, and

forest disturbance. The independent variables are IFMAs, log production, provincial income class, and slope.

The initial step in the analysis is to conduct descriptive statistics to examine the distribution of the variables and identify any outliers or missing data. Next is conducting multiple regression analysis to examine the combined effect of the independent variables on each dependent variable while controlling for potential confounding factors. The analysis also examines the interaction effects among the independent variables to determine whether any of the variables have a synergistic or antagonistic effect on each dependent variable.

The analysis is conducted using the software SPSS Statistics. The analysis results are presented in tables and graphs to facilitate the interpretation and communication of the findings. The significance of the results is evaluated using a p-value threshold of 0.05.

Challenges

Some challenges may arise when conducting this type of research. The availability and quality of the data can be a significant challenge, as accurate and reliable data is essential for conducting meaningful analysis. There may be missing or incomplete data.

The selection of the independent variables may be biased, as other factors not included in the model may also impact forest change. For instance, climate change, natural disasters, other forms of forest tenurial agreements, or even forest land-use plans may significantly impact forest cover, but these variables were not included in the model. The "Enter" approach in multiple regression modeling offers that flexibility to the researcher.

Interpreting the results may be challenging, as the relationships between the independent and dependent variables may be complex and difficult to explain. It may also be difficult to generalize the results to other regions or periods.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Patterns of Forest Change

According to the data (summarized in Table 1), the mean of forest loss is 5,828 hectares, while the mean of forest gain is 2,125 hectares, indicating that more forest was lost than gained. The median of forest loss is 3,474 hectares, and the median of forest gain is 1,333 hectares, providing further support for the idea that the amount of forest lost was generally higher than the amount gained (as the median is less susceptible to outliers than the mean). Additionally, the standard deviation of forest loss is 7,039 hectares, higher than the standard deviation of forest gain at 2,849 hectares, indicating greater variability in the amount of forest lost than gained. The range of forest loss is 45,438 hectares, while the range of forest gain is 18,129 hectares, suggesting greater extremes in the amount of forest lost than gained. The minimum value for forest loss is 43 hectares, while the minimum value for forest gain is 18 hectares, demonstrating that the amount of forest loss can be minimal in some provinces. The maximum value for forest loss is 45,481 hectares. The maximum value for forest gain is 18,147 hectares, indicating that the forest loss can be very large in other provinces. Finally, the sum of forest loss is 472,084 hectares. In comparison, the sum of forest gain is 172,161 hectares. This disparity further supports the idea that more forest is being lost than gained since the total sum of forest loss is larger than the total sum of forest gain. Table 1 further shows that stable forest has a higher mean, median, and smaller standard deviation, range, minimum, and maximum values compared to forest disturbance, which indicates that the amount of stable forest is higher, less variable, and has a narrower distribution than the forest disturbance. In contrast,

the forest disturbance has a lower mean, median, and larger standard deviation, range, minimum, and maximum values compared to stable forest, suggesting that the amount of forest disturbance is lower on average, more variable, and has a wider distribution than the stable forest. Overall, these differences imply that the stable forest is more consistent in terms of area coverage. In contrast, forest disturbance is a more dynamic process that involves frequent changes in the forest area.

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics for the Dependent Variables (ha)

Statistic	Stable forest	Forest loss	Forest gain	Forest disturbance
Mean	230784	5828	2125	19406
Median	196872	3474	1333	9560
Standard deviation	158892	7039	2849	28460
Range	938083	45438	18129	189418
Minimum	7373	43	18	18
Maximum	945456	45481	18147	189436
Sum	18693543	472084	172161	1571876

The following maps represent the forest loss and gain in different provinces of the Philippines in the 2000–2020 period. Figure 1 shows the forest loss, while Figure 2 shows the forest gain. The forest loss and gain are expressed in hectares; each polygon represents a province in the Philippines.

When comparing the two maps, it is apparent that some interesting patterns emerge. Firstly, some provinces appear on both top quintiles (darkest hues in the map), indicating that these provinces have both lost and gained forest cover in the specified period. For example, Agusan del Sur, Bukidnon, Cotabato, Davao del Norte, Davao del Sur, Davao Occidental, Palawan, Quezon, South Cotabato, Sultan Kudarat, Zamboanga del Norte, and Maguindanao all appear on both top

quintiles.

Secondly, the forest loss numbers are generally higher than the forest gain numbers (see map legends), which indicates that the Philippines is losing more forest cover than it is gaining. This trend is worrying, as forests provide essential ecosystem services, such as carbon sequestration, water regulation, and habitat for wildlife.

Thirdly, some provinces have experienced high levels of forest loss. Palawan, for example, lost 45,481 hectares of forest cover over the specified period, which is concerning, as Palawan is known for its rich biodiversity and unique ecosystems, and the loss of forest cover can have significant impacts on these systems.

Fourthly, some provinces have experienced high levels of forest gain. Cotabato, for example, has the highest forest gain (18,147 hectares), indicating that it has gained significant forest cover over the specified period. This positive trend indicates that efforts to reforest and restore degraded land in this province are paying off.

Overall, comparing the two maps highlights the need to manage forest change in the Philippines. While some provinces are making progress in forest regrowth, the country is losing more forest cover than it is gaining, signaling negative impacts on both the environment and the people who rely on these resources for their livelihoods.

Figure 1

Forest loss by province

Figure 2

Forest gain by province

Description of the Independent Variables

Descriptive statistics (Table 2) for the land area (in hectares) covered by IFMAs in 2010, log production (in cubic meters) in 2010, and share of land area over 18 percent slope computed using data from 80 provinces (plus Metro Manila, totaling to 81 cases) in the Philippines (see APPENDICES). The mean area for IFMAs was 12,590 hectares (Standard deviation (SD) = 34,928), the median was 0 hectares, and the range was 230,585 hectares. The minimum and maximum

values were 0 and 230,585 hectares, respectively. The sum of areas of IFMAs in 2010 was 1,019,795 hectares.

The mean logging production in 2010 was 6,871 cubic meters (SD = 14,862), the median was 820 cubic meters, and the range was 82,165 cubic meters. The minimum and maximum values were 0 and 82,165 cubic meters, respectively. The sum of log production in 2010 was 556,563 cubic meters.

The mean for the share of land area over 18 percent slope was 0.318 (SD = 0.168), the median was 0.284, and the range was 0.804. The minimum and maximum values were 0.031 and 0.835, respectively.

Overall, the data show that the area of IFMAs varied greatly across the provinces, with some provinces having no IFMAs while others had up to 230,585 hectares. The log production variable also varied widely across the provinces, ranging from no logging to 82,165 cubic meters. The share of land area over 18 percent slope had a relatively small range but also a high standard deviation, indicating that the values were more spread out than the other variables.

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics for the Independent Variables

Statistic	IFMAs (ha)	Log prod. (m ³)	Land > 18% slope
Mean	12590	6871	0.318
Median	0	820	0.284
Standard deviation	34928	14862	0.168
Range	230585	82165	0.804
Minimum	0	0	0.031
Maximum	230585	82165	0.835
Sum	1019795	556563	

There are five provincial income classes: 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, and 5th (see Figure 3). Of the 81 cases, 44.4% of the provinces are categorized as 1st class,

24.7% as 2nd class, 14.8% as 3rd class, 9.9% as 4th class, and 6.2% as 5th class.

Figure 3

Income class by province

Analysis of the Impact on Stable Forests

A standard multiple regression was run to predict stable forest from the land area covered by IFMAs, log production in 2010, provincial income class, and share of land area over 18 percent slope. There was linearity as assessed by partial

regression plots and a plot of studentized residuals against the predicted values. There was independence of residuals, as assessed by a Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.684. There was homoscedasticity, as assessed by visual inspection of a plot of studentized residuals versus unstandardized predicted values. There was no multicollinearity, as assessed by tolerance values greater than 0.1. The assumption of normality was met, as assessed by a P-P Plot (Laerd Statistics, 2015). The multiple regression model statistically significantly predicted stable forests, $F(4, 75) = 11.622$, $p < 0.001$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.35$. Only two variables added statistically significantly to the prediction, $p < 0.05$. Regression coefficients and standard errors can be found in Table 3. (See APPENDICES for Regression Outputs.)

Table 3

Multiple Regression Results for Stable Forest

Stable for.	B	95% CI for B		SE B	β
		LL	UL		
(Constant)	267685.835	198507.963	336863.706	34726.066	
IFMAs	1.049	-.014	2.111	.533	.233
Log prod.	1.349	-1.148	3.847	1.254	.128
Income cl.	-67898.581***	-95269.588	-40527.573	13739.761	-.486***
Slope	213814.618*	30680.674	396948.563	91929.997	.228*

*Note. Model = "Enter" method in SPSS Statistics; B = unstandardized regression coefficient; CI = confidence interval; LL = lower limit; UL = upper limit; SE B = standard error of the coefficient; β = standardized coefficient; Stable for. = stable forest (hectares); IFMAs = land area (hectares) covered by IFMAs in 2010; Log prod. = log production (cubic meters); Income cl. = income class; Slope = share of land area over 18 percent slope. * $p < 0.05$. ** $p < 0.01$. *** $p < 0.001$.*

Analysis of the Impact on Forest Loss

A multiple regression analysis was conducted to forecast forest loss based on several variables, including the land area covered by IFMAs, log production in

2010, provincial income class, and share of land area that is technically forestland (over 18 percent slope). The study found evidence of linearity, as assessed by partial regression plots and a plot of studentized residuals against predicted values. The residuals were independent, as indicated by a Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.098. Homoscedasticity was observed by visually examining a plot of studentized residuals versus unstandardized predicted values. Multicollinearity was not detected, as tolerance values were over 0.1. The assumption of normality was met, as shown by a P-P Plot (Laerd Statistics, 2015). The multiple regression model was statistically significant in predicting forest loss, with an F-statistic of (4, 75) = 8.683, $p < 0.001$, and an adjusted R^2 value of 0.28. Only one variable significantly impacted the prediction, with $p < 0.05$. Regression coefficients and standard errors can be found in Table 4. (See APPENDICES for Regression Outputs.)

Table 4

Multiple Regression Results for Forest Loss

For. loss	B	95% CI for B		SE B	β
		LL	UL		
(Constant)	10600.742	2873.056	18328.429	3879.162	
IFMAs	.176**	.058	.295	.060	.370**
Log prod.	.195	-.084	.474	.140	.174
Income cl.	-2912.357	-5969.904	145.189	1534.834	-.196
Slope	4019.518	-16437.915	24476.951	10269.269	.040

*Note. Model = "Enter" method in SPSS Statistics; B = unstandardized regression coefficient; CI = confidence interval; LL = lower limit; UL = upper limit; SE B = standard error of the coefficient; β = standardized coefficient; For. loss = forest loss (hectares); IFMAs = land area (hectares) covered by IFMAs in 2010; Log prod. = log production (cubic meters); Income cl. = income class; Slope = share of land area over 18 percent slope. * $p < 0.05$. ** $p < 0.01$. *** $p < 0.001$.*

Analysis of the Impact on Forest Gain

A multiple regression analysis was conducted to predict forest gain based on several variables, including the land area covered by IFMAs, log production in 2010, provincial income class, and share of land area over 18 percent slope. The linearity assumption was met, as indicated by the partial regression plots and a plot of studentized residuals against the predicted values. The independence assumption was also met, as shown by a Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.937. Additionally, homoscedasticity was verified by visually examining a plot of studentized residuals versus unstandardized predicted values. There was no multicollinearity, as assessed by tolerance values greater than 0.1. Normality was also satisfied, as determined by a P-P Plot (Laerd Statistics, 2015).

The multiple regression model was statistically significant in predicting forest gain ($F(4, 75) = 4.067, p < 0.001, \text{adjusted } R^2 = 0.134$). However, only one variable added significantly to the prediction, with $p < 0.05$. More information on the regression coefficients and standard errors can be found in Table 5. (See APPENDICES for Regression Outputs.)

Table 5

Multiple Regression Results for Forest Gain

For. gain	B	95% CI for B		SE B	β
		LL	UL		
(Constant)	4008.265	2562.113	5454.417	725.943	
IFMAs	.001	-.022	.023	.011	.007
Log prod.	.022	-.031	.074	.026	.113
Income cl.	-944.448**	-1516.634	-372.261	287.228	-.373**
Slope	-892.864	-4721.250	2935.522	1921.782	-.052

*Note. Model = "Enter" method in SPSS Statistics; B = unstandardized regression coefficient; CI = confidence interval; LL = lower limit; UL = upper limit; SE B = standard error of the coefficient; β = standardized coefficient; For. gain = forest gain (hectares); IFMAs = land area (hectares) covered by IFMAs in 2010; Log prod. = log production (cubic meters); Income cl. = income class; Slope = share of land area over 18 percent slope. * $p < 0.05$. ** $p < 0.01$. *** $p < 0.001$.*

Analysis of the Impact on Forest Disturbance

This analysis used multiple regression to predict forest disturbance based on several variables, including the land area covered by IFMAs, log production in 2010, provincial income class, and share of land area over 18 percent slope. The linearity assumption was satisfied, as indicated by the partial regression plots and a plot of studentized residuals against the predicted values. The independence assumption was also met, as evidenced by a Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.115. Additionally, homoscedasticity was observed, as confirmed by visually inspecting a plot of studentized residuals versus unstandardized predicted values. There was no multicollinearity, as assessed by tolerance values greater than 0.1. Normality was also met, as determined by a P-P Plot (Laerd Statistics, 2015).

The multiple regression model was found to be statistically significant in predicting forest disturbance ($F(4, 75) = 8.185, p < 0.001, \text{adj. } R^2 = 0.267$). However, only two variables added significantly to the prediction, with $p < 0.05$. More detailed information on the regression coefficients and standard errors can be found in Table 6. (See APPENDICES for Regression Outputs.)

Table 6

Multiple Regression Results for Forest Disturbance

For. dist.	B	95% CI for B		SE B	β
		LL	UL		
(Constant)	20095.763	6809.386	33382.140	6669.526	
IFMAs	.288**	.084	.492	.102	.354**
Log prod.	.322	-.157	.802	.241	.169
Income cl.	-5289.334*	-10546.239	-32.429	2638.873	-.209*
Slope	10584.888	-24588.015	45757.791	17656.174	.062

*Note. Model = "Enter" method in SPSS Statistics; B = unstandardized regression coefficient; CI = confidence interval; LL = lower limit; UL = upper limit; SE B = standard error of the coefficient; β = standardized coefficient; For. dist. = forest disturbance (hectares); IFMAs = land area (hectares) covered by IFMAs in 2010; Log prod. = log production (cubic meters); Income cl. = income class; Slope = share of land area over 18 percent slope. * $p < 0.05$. ** $p < 0.01$. *** $p < 0.001$.*

Interpretation of the Results

Only two predictor variables (provincial income class and share of land area over 18 percent slope) were statistically significant in predicting stable forests, with p-values less than 0.05. The coefficient for provincial income class was -67,899, indicating that as the income class of the province "increased" (e.g., from 4th class to 5th class)³, the area of stable forest decreased. The coefficient for the share of land area over 18 percent slope was 213,815, indicating that as the share of land area over 18 percent slope increased, the amount of stable forest increased.

Only one variable (land area covered by IFMAs in 2010) was found to have a statistically significant effect on the prediction of forest loss from 2011 to 2021. The regression coefficient for the land area covered by IFMAs was reported to be 0.176, which means that for every one-hectare increase of land covered by IFMAs in 2010, forest loss from 2011 to 2021 was predicted to increase by a 0.176 hectare, holding the other predictors constant.

The land area covered by IFMAs in 2010, log production in 2010, provincial income class, and the share of land area over 18 percent slope explain about 13.4% of the variation in forest gain. However, only one of the variables, provincial income class, added significant predictive power, with a regression coefficient of -944, indicating that for each unit "increase" in the variable (e.g., from 4th class to 5th class), the predicted forest gain decreases by about 944 hectares. The significance level of this variable was reported as $p < 0.05$, indicating a statistically

³ The change from 4th class to 5th class is, in fact, a decrease in provincial income class. The ordinal variable was encoded so that "1" denotes the 1st class (richer), "2" denotes the 2nd class... and "5" denotes the 5th class (poorer).

significant relationship between provincial income class and forest gain.

Only two independent variables, land area covered by IFMAs and provincial income class, had a significant relationship with forest disturbance. Specifically, the regression coefficient for the land area covered by IFMAs was 0.288, indicating that as the amount of land covered by IFMAs increased, so did the area of forest disturbance. However, this positive relationship may not suggest that IFMAs negatively impact forest ecosystems due to the low predicted value. On the other hand, the coefficient for the provincial income class was -5,289, which means that the forest disturbance level decreased as the province's income class "increased." This relationship suggests that wealthier provinces may be better able to protect their forest ecosystems.

Comparison with Previous Studies

One of the findings is that the provincial income class positively impacts forest stability, consistent with other related studies. In their analysis of the institutional framework for forest management in the Philippines, the researchers (Guiang, Esguerra, & Bacalla, 2007) saw that the capacity of local governments to manage forests was hindered by a lack of resources, including financial resources, and that increasing the resources available to local governments could help improve forest management and conservation. Another study (Andersson, 2013) found that the strength of local institutions, including local governments, was a key determinant of forest conservation in Bolivia — and that local governments with better allocations were more effective at implementing and enforcing forest policies (Kamugisha-Ruhombe, 2010).

Another finding is that increased land area covered by IFMAs leads to

increased forest loss. Different studies have produced varying results depending on the context and specific conditions of the FMAs. Some studies have found a positive relationship between FMAs and forest loss, indicating that implementing FMAs may not always effectively prevent deforestation. For example, a study (Brandt, Nolte, & Agrawal, 2016) found that, in some cases, implementing FMAs in Congo did not lead to decreased deforestation. However, other studies have found that when implemented correctly, FMAs can effectively reduce deforestation. For example, a study in the Congo Basin (Tritsch, et al., 2020) found that community forest management agreements were associated with lower deforestation rates than those without agreements.

The regression model also suggests that a lower provincial income class predicts a decreased forest gain. Other studies have also found a positive relationship between government income and forest gain, suggesting that better-funded governments are more likely to invest in forest conservation programs and enforce regulations to curb deforestation. For example, a study by Frédéric, et al. (Determination of tropical deforestation rates and related carbon losses from 1990 to 2010, 2014) found that countries with higher GDP per capita successfully reduced forest loss. However, other research suggests that lower-income governments may also be able to promote forest gain by implementing policies that prioritize sustainable forestry practices and involve local communities in forest management. For example, a study by Craig (Benefits and Constraints of Community-Based Forest Management in the Philippines, 2018) found that community-based forestry program in four pilot barangays successfully increased forest cover despite the relatively low per capita income.

Several studies have examined forest disturbance's relationship with

provincial incomes. While the exact findings may vary depending on the specific context and methods used, some evidence suggests that decreased government incomes can lead to increased forest disturbance. For example, a study by Larson (Decentralisation and forest management in Latin America: towards a working model, 2003) found that decreased capacities in local governments in Indonesia were associated with failure to curb deforestation. Another study by Ardiansyah and Jotzo (2013) found that lower levels of government spending on forest conservation in Indonesia were linked to higher levels of deforestation.

CONCLUSION

Summary

Several variables were analyzed with forest stability, loss, gain, and disturbance. Only two predictor variables, provincial income class and share of land area over 18 percent slope, were statistically significant in predicting stable forests. The land area covered by IFMAs in 2010 was found to have a statistically significant effect on the prediction of forest loss from 2011 to 2021. Regarding forest gain, only the provincial income class added significant predictive power. Regarding forest disturbance, only land area covered by IFMAs and provincial income class had a significant relationship, with wealthier provinces being better able to protect their forest ecosystems. The overall analysis suggests that certain factors, such as income and land use, may impact forest health and preservation.

Contributions of the Study

This study makes valuable contributions to our understanding of forest change in the Philippines by employing a quantitative approach with the following highlights:

1. The study provides a quantitative analysis of the impact of forest management agreements, log production, provincial income class, and slope on forest change in the Philippines.
2. The study utilizes multiple regression analysis to identify significant variables that predict forest change, allowing for a more precise understanding of the relationships between the variables.
3. The study assesses the assumptions of multiple regression analysis, such as linearity, independence of residuals, homoscedasticity,

multicollinearity, and normality, to ensure the validity of the statistical analysis.

4. The study analyzes forest change from different perspectives, including stable forest, forest loss, forest gain, and forest disturbance, providing a comprehensive understanding of the factors that influence forest change.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Policy Recommendations

Based on the research findings, the following are recommended for policy:

1. Conservation policies should prioritize the protection of stable forests in provinces with a high share of land area over 18 percent slope; these forests in steeper slopes are often biodiversity centers, and they play a crucial role in mitigating the effects of climate change.
2. Government interventions should focus on reducing forest loss in provinces with lower income classes, as these provinces are more likely to experience forest loss due to their reduced revenues.
3. Forest tenurial instruments should be managed carefully to minimize their impact on forest disturbance. The positive relationship between the land area covered by IFMAs and forest disturbance suggests that the former may have unintended negative consequences on forest ecosystems.

These recommendations highlight the importance of sustainable forest management and conservation efforts, particularly in provinces with a high forest loss and degradation risk. Policymakers should prioritize the protection of stable forests and encourage provinces to protect their forest ecosystems actively.

Future Research Directions

Based on the results borne out of the analysis, the following are some potential future research directions:

1. Identification of other predictors: Although only a few predictors were found to be statistically significant, there may be other variables that are

relevant to predicting forest stability, loss, gain, and disturbance. Future research could explore additional variables that could be included in the model to improve the predictive power.

2. Spatial analysis: The research could incorporate spatial analysis to explore the relationship between the predictors and the forest variables at different geographic scales. This investigation helps identify specific regions where certain variables strongly influence forest stability, loss, gain, and disturbance.
3. Historical analysis: The study could include a longer time frame to examine the historical patterns of forest stability, loss, gain, and disturbance. This extended examination could provide insights into the factors that have driven changes in forest ecosystems over time and inform future conservation efforts.
4. Comparative analysis: The study could include a comparative analysis of regions or countries to identify common patterns or factors influencing forest stability, loss, gain, and disturbance. This comparison helps inform conservation efforts and policies across different contexts.

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APPENDICES

Independent and Dependent Variables

Table 7

Stable Forest, Forest Loss, Gain, and Disturbance by Province

Province	Stable (ha)	Loss (ha)	Gain (ha)	Disturbance (ha)
Abra	308530	856	736	7233
Agusan del Norte	225479	3287	1481	24199
Agusan del Sur	608755	24005	3876	133117
Aklan	118385	2071	295	5706
Albay	185567	2131	628	9800
Antique	181951	1774	514	3219
Apayao	292778	7300	280	60648
Aurora	260346	2473	659	15770
Basilan	107337	1577	286	14771
Bataan	82002	925	1642	1469
Batanes	12552	70	18	649
Batangas	187661	4397	1385	5911
Benguet	222141	1734	203	2641
Biliran	43699	728	130	1305
Bohol	243191	2610	2929	5196
Bukidnon	543965	23536	11434	27055
Bulacan	133949	1846	1126	5689
Cagayan	480962	24659	2060	44762
Camarines Norte	164182	1964	455	11957
Camarines Sur	348578	5893	1361	18768
Camiguin	22930	43	36	305
Capiz	107805	7125	1168	10205
Catanduanes	129182	298	94	5298
Cavite	64627	1512	761	1424
Cebu	302141	4269	2579	9727
Davao de Oro	332242	9445	3064	48232
Davao del Norte	233910	10366	3856	24788
Davao del Sur	458759	9731	4017	23264
Davao Oriental	413007	10124	2604	53762
Dinagat Islands	61925	2468	285	2339
Eastern Samar	345035	9009	317	33417
Guimaras	34472	416	1657	1976
Ifugao	169408	2089	1103	8626
Ilocos Norte	221078	927	372	3694
Ilocos Sur	159967	743	512	1810

Province	Stable (ha)	Loss (ha)	Gain (ha)	Disturbance (ha)
Iloilo	193773	7107	2528	9054
Isabela	507252	15140	3189	38285
Kalinga	197488	4226	578	15478
La Union	89353	610	379	1003
Laguna	116235	2392	734	7488
Lanao del Norte	224027	4634	1333	10852
Lanao del Sur	288413	5699	1545	13915
Leyte	358850	11752	1947	46035
Maguindanao	188591	13326	6285	10653
Marinduque	75021	634	446	3908
Masbate	193974	2762	3342	7660
Metropolitan Manila	7373	258	448	18
Misamis Occidental	160761	1411	467	7246
Misamis Oriental	252252	3635	1591	8280
Mountain Province	174631	2511	332	6113
Negros Occidental	306104	5841	4289	9560
Negros Oriental	289536	4064	3301	8248
Cotabato	331156	18280	18147	21633
Northern Samar	262502	4126	315	20407
Nueva Ecija	180115	2550	3453	4956
Nueva Vizcaya	286936	2510	941	16587
Occidental Mindoro	347448	7425	1346	26291
Oriental Mindoro	258389	8595	1405	27838
Palawan	945456	45481	11061	189436
Pampanga	33254	787	1916	1008
Pangasinan	172254	2631	3056	2683
Quezon	654735	12076	3743	54157
Quirino	226310	4832	473	24661
Rizal	91949	1270	1038	5328
Romblon	104662	646	494	6862
Samar	414023	9076	1607	49107
Sarangani	220273	6905	2494	14681
Siquijor	21700	76	277	292
Sorsogon	156316	923	298	6779
South Cotabato	246822	12106	9278	16035
Southern Leyte	151113	402	259	4281
Sultan Kudarat	257474	9131	5848	23629
Sulu	110937	2797	897	5190
Surigao del Norte	151551	3474	843	4656
Surigao del Sur	327396	8101	1139	46941
Tarlac	88278	1828	2347	5584
Tawi-Tawi	76024	5191	491	13011
Zambales	196872	4496	3595	5145
Zamboanga del Norte	445247	11584	4152	82397
Zamboanga del Sur	335412	9013	2291	30982

Province	Stable (ha)	Loss (ha)	Gain (ha)	Disturbance (ha)
Zamboanga Sibugay	166809	7371	2298	28790

Table 8

Income Class, IFMA, Log Production, and > 18% Slope by Province

Province	Income class	IFMA 2010 (ha)	Log prod. 2010 (M ³)	> 18% slope
Abra	3rd	0	6	0.639
Agusan del Norte	3rd	4772	82165	0.429
Agusan del Sur	1st	230585	69784	0.249
Aklan	2nd	0	8326	0.366
Albay	1st	0	126	0.193
Antique	2nd	0	2640	0.493
Apayao	3rd	43476	15455	0.596
Aurora	3rd	130458	24836	0.611
Basilan	3rd	0	0	0.084
Bataan	1st	1136	1140	0.256
Batanes	5th	0	0	0.273
Batangas	1st	100	0	0.142
Benguet	2nd	0	184	0.835
Biliran	4th	1834	28	0.462
Bohol	1st	0	95	0.102
Bukidnon	1st	40944	18259	0.326
Bulacan	1st	1949	2136	0.242
Cagayan	1st	0	144	0.260
Camarines Norte	2nd	0	65	0.143
Camarines Sur	1st	0	862	0.183
Camiguin	5th	0	391	0.472
Capiz	1st	0	10513	0.206
Catanduanes	3rd	0	0	0.469
Cavite	1st	0	0	0.063
Cebu	1st	1132	1714	0.265
Davao de Oro	1st	0	38501	0.376
Davao del Norte	1st	20833	14815	0.282
Davao del Sur	1st	2478	5888	0.325
Davao Oriental	1st	82443	49677	0.498
Dinagat Islands	4th	0	0	0.480
Eastern Samar	2nd	0	0	0.206
Guimaras	4th	0	459	0.031
Ifugao	3rd	0	589	0.597
Ilocos Norte	1st	250	102	0.402
Ilocos Sur	1st	995	162	0.435
Iloilo	1st	541	12207	0.193

Province	Income class	IFMA 2010 (ha)	Log prod. 2010 (M ³)	> 18% slope
Isabela	1st	88051	35838	0.287
Kalinga	3rd	0	0	0.561
La Union	1st	0	104	0.329
Laguna	1st	0	411	0.139
Lanao del Norte	2nd	0	3690	0.289
Lanao del Sur	1st	21403	0	0.233
Leyte	1st	572	862	0.245
Maguindanao	1st	29590	0	0.189
Marinduque	4th	0	66	0.404
Masbate	1st	0	0	0.108
Metropolitan Manila	1st	0	0	
Misamis Occidental	2nd	0	18786	0.274
Misamis Oriental	1st	12634	1599	0.374
Mountain Province	4th	0	0	0.709
Negros Occidental	1st	15575	24211	0.185
Negros Oriental	1st	6855	1547	0.321
Cotabato	1st	724	6641	0.177
Northern Samar	2nd	0	0	0.180
Nueva Ecija	1st	877	1045	0.223
Nueva Vizcaya	2nd	0	6977	0.600
Occidental Mindoro	2nd	0	180	0.523
Oriental Mindoro	1st	0	820	0.367
Palawan	1st	0	169	0.361
Pampanga	1st	0	227	0.080
Pangasinan	1st	1464	1189	0.133
Quezon	1st	14527	7747	0.235
Quirino	3rd	7793	2986	0.559
Rizal	1st	0	0	0.371
Romblon	3rd	0	0	0.477
Samar	1st	550	4	0.243
Sarangani	2nd	3602	2296	0.509
Siquijor	5th	0	0	0.132
Sorsogon	2nd	0	155	0.170
South Cotabato	1st	6852	9697	0.312
Southern Leyte	3rd	0	3579	0.446
Sultan Kudarat	1st	28938	1007	0.342
Sulu	2nd	0	0	0.065
Surigao del Norte	2nd	9328	2928	0.300
Surigao del Sur	1st	115455	12790	0.242
Tarlac	1st	6981	3708	0.209
Tawi-Tawi	3rd	0	0	0.058
Zambales	2nd	9983	16	0.451
Zamboanga del Norte	1st	71643	37417	0.361
Zamboanga del Sur	1st	599	4730	0.275

Province	Income class	IFMA 2010 (ha)	Log prod. 2010 (M ³)	> 18% slope
Zamboanga Sibugay	2nd	1873	1872	0.174

Data on Forest Extent Change

Figure 4

Forest extent data (sampled in Boracay Is.) in 2000 and 2020

Figure 5

Forest loss and gain data (sampled in Boracay Is.)

Regression Outputs

Stable forest

Table 9

Stable forest: model summary

Model summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.619 ^a	0.383	0.350	1.27313451E5	1.684

a. Predictors: (Constant), Share of land area over 18% slope, Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010, Income class, Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010

b. Dependent Variable: Stable forest (GFW)

Figure 6

Stable forest: scatterplot

Table 10*Stable forest: correlations*

		Correlations				
		Stable forest (GFW)	Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010	Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010	Income class	Share of land area over 18% slope
Pearson Correlation	Stable forest (GFW)	1.000	.402	.358	-.457	.093
	Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010	.402	1.000	.64	-.144	.077
	Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010	.358	.640	1.000	-.117	.105
	Income class	-.457	-.144	-.117	1.000	.341
	Share of land area over 18% slope	.093	.077	.105	.341	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Stable forest (GFW)		.000	0.001	.000	.206
	Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010	.000		.000	.102	.248
	Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010	.001	.000		.151	.176
	Income class	.000	.102	.151		.001
	Share of land area over 18% slope	.206	.248	.176	.001	
N	Stable forest (GFW)	80	80	80	80	80
	Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010	80	80	80	80	80
	Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010	80	80	80	80	80
	Income class	80	80	80	80	80
	Share of land area over 18% slope	80	80	80	80	80

Table 11*Stable forest: outliers*

Casewise Diagnostics ^a				
Case Number	Std. Residual	Stable forest (GFW)	Predicted Value	Residual
2	5.249	9.45456E5	2.7720235E5	6.6825E5

a. Dependent Variable: Stable forest (GFW)

Figure 7

Stable forest: histogram

Figure 8

Stable forest: P-P plot

Table 12*Stable forest: model significance*

ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	7.535E11	4	1.884E11	11.622	.000 ^a
	Residual	1.216E12	75	1.621E10		
	Total	1.969E12	79			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Share of land area over 18% slope, Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010, Income class, Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010

b. Dependent Variable: Stable forest (GFW)

Table 13*Stable forest: coefficients*

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	267685.835	34726.066		7.708	.000	198508	336863.7
	Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010	1.049	.533	.233	1.965	.053	-.014	2.111
	Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010	1.349	1.254	.128	1.076	.285	-1.148	3.847
	Income class	-67898.581	13739.761	-.486	-4.942	.000	-95269.6	-40527.6
	Share of land area over 18% slope	213814.618	91929.997	.228	2.326	.023	30680.67	396948.6

a. Dependent Variable: Stable forest (GFW)

Table 14*Stable forest: prediction*

Contrast Results (K Matrix) ^a			Dependent Variable
Contrast			Stable forest (GFW)
L1	Contrast Estimate		35100.241
	Hypothesized Value		0
	Difference (Estimate - Hypothesized)		35100.241
	Std. Error		42709.513
	Sig.		.414
	95% Confidence Interval for Difference	Lower Bound	-49981.471
		Upper Bound	120181.95

a. Based on the user-specified contrast coefficients (L') matrix number 1

Forest loss**Table 15***Forest loss: model summary*

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.563 ^a	.317	.280	1.42218660E4	2.098

a. Predictors: (Constant), Share of land area over 18% slope, Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010, Income class, Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010
b. Dependent Variable: Forest loss from 2011 to 2021

Figure 9

Forest loss: scatterplot

Table 16*Forest loss: correlations*

		Correlations				
		Forest loss from 2011 to 2021	Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010	Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010	Income class	Share of land area over 18% slope
Pearson Correlation	Forest loss from 2011 to 2021	1.000	.512	.438	-.256	.020
	Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010	.512	1.000	.640	-.144	.077
	Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010	.438	.640	1.000	-.117	.105
	Income class	-.256	-.144	-.117	1.000	.341
	Share of land area over 18% slope	.020	.077	.105	.341	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Forest loss from 2011 to 2021		.000	.000	.011	.430
	Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010	.000		.000	.102	.248
	Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010	.000	.000		.151	.176
	Income class	.011	.102	.151		.001
	Share of land area over 18% slope	.430	.248	.176	.001	
N	Forest loss from 2011 to 2021	80	80	80	80	80
	Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010	80	80	80	80	80
	Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010	80	80	80	80	80
	Income class	80	80	80	80	80
	Share of land area over 18% slope	80	80	80	80	80

Table 17*Forest loss: outliers*

Casewise Diagnostics ^a				
Case Number	Std. Residual	Forest loss from 2011 to 2021	Predicted Value	Residual
59	7.22	1.11855878E5	9.17242050E3	1.0268E5

a. Dependent Variable: Forest loss from 2011 to 2021

Figure 10

Forest loss: histogram

Figure 11

Forest loss: P-P plot

Table 18*Forest loss: model significance*

ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	7.025E9	4	1.756E9	8.683	.000a
	Residual	1.517E10	75	2.023E8		
	Total	2.219E10	79			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Share of land area over 18% slope, Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010, Income class, Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010

b. Dependent Variable: Forest loss from 2011 to 2021

Table 19*Forest loss: coefficients*

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients B	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
							Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	10600.742	3879.162		2.733	.008	2873.056	18328.429
	Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010	.176	.060	.370	2.960	.004	.058	.295
	Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010	.195	.140	.174	1.394	.167	-.084	.474
	Income class	-2912.357	1534.834	-.196	-1.898	.062	-5969.9	145.189
	Share of land area over 18% slope	4019.518	10269.269	.040	.391	.697	-16437.9	24476.95

a. Dependent Variable: Forest loss from 2011 to 2021

Table 20*Forest loss: prediction*

Contrast Results (K Matrix) ^a			Dependent Variable
Contrast			Forest loss from 2011 to 2021
L1	Contrast Estimate		4431.672
	Hypothesized Value		0
	Difference (Estimate - Hypothesized)		4431.672
	Std. Error		2998.209
	Sig.		.144
	95% Confidence Interval for Difference	Lower Bound	-1541.068
		Upper Bound	10404.412

a. Based on the user-specified contrast coefficients (L') matrix number 1

Forest gain**Table 21***Forest gain: model summary*

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.422 ^a	0.178	0.134	2.66E+03	1.937

a. Predictors: (Constant), Share of land area over 18% slope, Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010, Income class, Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010
b. Dependent Variable: Forest gain (GFW)

Figure 12

Forest gain: scatterplot

Table 22*Forest gain: correlations*

		Correlations				
		Forest gain (GFW)	Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010	Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010	Income class	Share of land area over 18% slope
Pearson Correlation	Forest gain (GFW)	1.000	.128	.155	-.405	-.167
	Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010	.128	1.000	.640	-.144	.077
	Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010	.155	.640	1.000	-.117	.105
	Income class	-.405	-.144	-.117	1.000	.341
	Share of land area over 18% slope	-.167	.077	.105	.341	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Forest gain (GFW)		.128	.085	.000	.069
	Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010	.128		.000	.102	.248
	Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010	.085	.000		.151	.176
	Income class	.000	.102	.151		.001
	Share of land area over 18% slope	.069	.248	.176	.001	
N	Forest gain (GFW)	80	80	80	80	80
	Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010	80	80	80	80	80
	Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010	80	80	80	80	80
	Income class	80	80	80	80	80
	Share of land area over 18% slope	80	80	80	80	80

Table 23*Forest gain: outliers*

Casewise Diagnostics ^a				
Case Number	Std. Residual	Forest gain (GFW)	Predicted Value	Residual
2	3.125	1.10611556E4	2.74513918E3	8.3160E3
49	5.673	1.81474659E4	3.04945416E3	1.5098E4
54	3.098	1.14341740E4	3.18927003E3	8.2449E3

a. Dependent Variable: Forest gain (GFW)

Figure 13

Forest gain: histogram

Figure 14

Forest gain: P-P plot

Table 24*Forest gain: model significance*

ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.152E8	4	2.881E7	4.067	.005 ^a
	Residual	5.313E8	75	7083408.374		
	Total	6.465E8	79			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Share of land area over 18% slope, Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010, Income class, Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010

b. Dependent Variable: Forest gain (GFW)

Table 25*Forest gain: coefficients*

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients B	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
							Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	4008.265	725.943		5.521	.000	2562.113	5454.417
	Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010	.001	.011	.007	.049	.961	-.022	.023
	Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010	.022	.026	.113	.823	.413	-.031	.074
	Income class	-.944.448	287.228	-.373	-3.288	.002	-1516.63	-372.261
	Share of land area over 18% slope	-.892.864	1921.782	-.052	-.465	.644	-4721.25	2935.522

a. Dependent Variable: Forest gain (GFW)

Table 26*Forest gain: prediction*

Contrast Results (K Matrix) ^a			Dependent Variable
Contrast			Forest gain (GFW)
L1	Contrast Estimate		2617.385
	Hypothesized Value		0
	Difference (Estimate - Hypothesized)		2617.385
	Std. Error		616.502
	Sig.		0
	95% Confidence Interval for Difference	Lower Bound	1389.250
		Upper Bound	3845.520

a. Based on the user-specified contrast coefficients (L') matrix number 1

Forest disturbance**Table 27***Forest disturbance: model summary*

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.551 ^a	.304	.267	2.45E4	2.115

a. Predictors: (Constant), Share of land area over 18% slope, Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010, Income class, Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010
b. Dependent Variable: Disturbed forest (GFW)

Figure 15

Forest disturbance: scatterplot

Table 28*Forest disturbance: correlations*

		Correlations				
		Disturbed forest (GFW)	Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010	Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010	Income class	Share of land area over 18% slope
Pearson Correlation	Disturbed forest (GFW)	1.000	.497	.426	-.259	.036
	Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010	.497	1.000	.640	-.144	.077
	Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010	.426	.640	1.000	-.117	.105
	Income class	-.259	-.144	-.117	1	.341
	Share of land area over 18% slope	.036	.077	.105	.341	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Disturbed forest (GFW)		.000	.000	.010	.376
	Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010	.000		.000	.102	.248
	Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010	.000	.000		.151	.176
	Income class	.010	.102	.151		.001
	Share of land area over 18% slope	.376	.248	.176	.001	
N	Disturbed forest (GFW)	80	80	80	80	80
	Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010	80	80	80	80	80
	Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010	80	80	80	80	80
	Income class	80	80	80	80	80
	Share of land area over 18% slope	80	80	80	80	80

Table 29*Forest disturbance: outliers*

Casewise Diagnostics ^a				
Case Number	Std. Residual	Disturbed forest (GFW)	Predicted Value	Residual
3	6.983	1.89435796E5	1.86820677E4	1.7075E5

a. Dependent Variable: Disturbed forest (GFW)

Figure 16

Forest disturbance: histogram

Figure 17

Forest disturbance: P-P plot

Table 30*Forest disturbance: model significance*

ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.958E10	4	4.894E9	8.185	.000 ^a
	Residual	4.484E10	75	5.979E8		
	Total	6.442E10	79			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Share of land area over 18% slope, Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010, Income class, Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010

b. Dependent Variable: Disturbed forest (GFW)

Table 31*Forest disturbance: coefficients*

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	20095.763	6669.526		3.013	.004	6809.386	33382.14
	Land area (in has.) covered by IFMAs in 2010	.288	.102	.354	2.807	.006	.084	.492
	Log production (in cu. m.) in 2010	.322	.241	.169	1.339	.185	-.157	.802
	Income class	-5289.334	2638.873	-.209	-2.004	.049	-10546.2	-32.429
	Share of land area over 18% slope	10584.888	17656.174	.062	.600	.551	-24588	45757.79

a. Dependent Variable: Disturbed forest (GFW)

Table 32*Forest disturbance: prediction*

Contrast Results (K Matrix) ^a			Dependent Variable
Contrast			Disturbed forest (GFW)
L1	Contrast Estimate		22975.384
	Hypothesized Value		0
	Difference (Estimate - Hypothesized)		22975.384
	Std. Error		5640.999
	Sig.		.000
	95% Confidence Interval for Difference	Lower Bound	11737.937
		Upper Bound	34212.831

a. Based on the user-specified contrast coefficients (L') matrix number 1